

Observations of free and bound gravity-capillary waves

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Extended Abstract

Gravity-capillary and capillary waves play an important role in air-sea interaction processes and radar backscatter from the sea surface. It has long been known that radar Doppler spectra of the vertical and horizontal polarizations show different spectral peaks, with the vertical polarization having a peak at lower Doppler frequency that corresponds to Bragg scattering from free capillary waves [1]. The peak in the horizontal spectrum occurs at higher Doppler frequencies and is associated with scattering from bound capillary waves that travel at the phase speed of the generating longer wave. For improved models of the backscatter at high radar frequencies and small grazing angles it is therefore necessary to include the contribution of the non-Bragg scattering components as a function of wind speed, surface films, and background wave conditions.

We report measurements of parasitic capillary waves generated by wind as well as by mechanically generated gravity waves. The experiments were conducted at the NASA Air-Sea Interaction Facility at Wallops Flight Facility (Wallops Island, VA). An imaging slope gauge was used to collect the alongwind component of the surface slope at sampling rates of up to 120 Hz for fetches of 5m and 10m and with wind speeds ranging from 5 to 12 m/s. In addition, mechanically generated gravity waves with frequencies of 0.9 Hz were superimposed on the wind waves.

The wave component propagating in alongwind direction is extracted from every image in the sequence, and from the resulting space-time image (see Fig.1), the corresponding frequency-wavenumber spectra is obtained (see Fig.2). For purely mechanically generated waves the frequency-wavenumber spectrum consists only of the bound harmonics. For the wind-generated waves on the other hand, the spectrum shows multiple branches near the dispersion curve for free gravity-capillary waves. At high wind speed, the advection of the short waves by the longer waves causes spreading of the spectral densities and different branches cannot be distinguished.

References

[1] P. H. Y. Lee, J. D. Barter, E. Caponi, M. Caponi, C. L. Hindman, B. M. Lake, and Rungaldier, 1996, Wind-speed Dependence of small-grazing-angle microwave backscatter from sea surfaces, IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, Vol. 44, No.3, 333-340.

Figure 1 Space-time image for a mechanically generated wave of 0.9 Hz (left side). Space-time image for pure wind waves at a wind speed of 8.4m/s (right side). The waves are propagating from left to right.

Figure 2 Frequency-wavenumber spectra of the space-time images shown in Fig. 1.